

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OPPORTUNITIES OF DIGITAL SKILLS IN BIOLOGY TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the perspectives of the application of digital skills, 3D technologies, STEAM method in the teaching of biology are brought to attention. The importance of biology teachers' digital skills was highlighted by showing the works done in this field as an example. The necessity of increasing the technological literacy of both high school and high school biology teachers is also highlighted in the article. The author illustrated the usefulness of digital skills in the article with the following examples: Easy Access to Information and Resources: Through the Internet, students can easily access vast databases, e-books and educational videos, making learning more accessible. Improved Collaboration and Communication: Digital platforms allow students and teachers to collaborate and communicate better. Online classes, forums and group work enhance the quality of education. Critical Thinking and Problem Solving: Simulations, interactive games and virtual labs help students develop critical thinking and problem solving skills. Importance of Digital Skills to the Job Market: Digital skills such as programming, data analysis and other technical skills are extremely important in today's job market. Technologies prepare students for the future world of work. Enhancing Interest and Engagement in Education: Through digital tools, videos, games and interactive applications, learning becomes more fun and engaging, which increases student engagement. Supporting Teachers and Improving the Quality of Education: Using digital tools, teachers can organize lesson plans more efficiently and manage the learning process better. Lifelong Learning Opportunities: Digital technologies aren't just for school; With online courses, certificate programs, and training, people of all ages have access to learning. Creating Educational Equity: Digital tools help close educational inequities as educational resources become easier to access, even in low-income areas. Learning Process Analysis and Development: Digital tools and data help track student progress and improve areas of learning. The relevance of the article is to discuss the things to be done to solve the mentioned issues.

Keywords: Game-based learning, Labster, Classcraft, AR, VR, MR, PhET, Interactive Simulations, Quizlet.

At a time when 21st century skills are becoming more relevant, educational institutions have placed a requirement on training young people with creative and different ways of thinking. Improvement of pedagogical personnel, correct selection of personnel with special skills is of particular importance in fulfilling the duties arising from these requirements. But what is the importance of digital skills and technologies in education? Digital technologies have already become an integral part of the modern educational process. The development of digital skills in education creates new learning and teaching opportunities for both students and teachers. Therefore, the research conducted in this field shows how the integration of technologies into the teaching process can be useful for the study of biology. Impact of digital technologies on the teaching process: Unlike traditional educational approaches, digital technologies can make biology teaching more interactive and engaging. Among researchers who have elaborated on this, noted educational methodologist Richard E. Mayer, in his book "Multimedia Learning," notes how multimedia technologies and digital tools can help students better understand biological concepts. He emphasizes that digital technologies strengthen students' memory and enable them to participate more actively in the research process (Mayer, 2005). Simulations and interactive teaching tools: Teaching biology in a more

visual and visual manner leads to better student absorption of information. Educators such as John Dewey emphasized the importance of teaching based on practical experiences. In this sense, simulations and interactive programs in the field of biology allow students to better understand living organisms, ecosystems and biological processes. For example, programs such as Virtual Labs allow students to safely conduct various biological experiments and immediately evaluate the results of experiments. Education and use of digital platforms: Digital platforms such as microblogging and forums can be used for discussions and information sharing among students in biology teaching. This allows students to explore issues more deeply and evaluate each other's ideas. In Constructivist Learning Environments, David H. Jonassen notes how important it is for students to think about creating and constructing their own experiences (Jonassen, 1999). Experiments show that the use of new, different, research-oriented, creative and efficient methods and methods, which have begun to be used effectively in the field of education in recent years, has come to the fore. Adapting new methods and technologies to each discipline, taking into account the emerging needs, requires the integration skills of subject teachers. The use of innovations in biology teaching plays a special role in improving the teaching process and research skills. Especially in biology teaching,

the use of visualization, experimentation and observation is necessary, and the use of various new methods and tools plays a special role in increasing mastery (Babayeva, 2024; 2023).

The teaching of biological knowledge with various pedagogical technologies has already made it possible to achieve important achievements in this field:

Online courses and learning resources for biology topics: Online learning resources and open learning materials allow students to learn biology topics at their own pace. On the Khan Academy platform created by Salman Khan, the study of biological topics is accessible to students of various levels. Through online videos, animations and quizzes, students can deepen biology topics anytime and anywhere. These types of resources attract students' attention during the lesson and help them to be more active in learning.

Data analytics and personalized learning: Digital technologies also allow students to track their learning progress and identify their strengths and weaknesses. Using data mining and Learning Analytics technologies, teachers can better track student progress and personalize the learning process to each student's needs. This approach allows to increase the quality of biological teaching and to develop the potential of each student to the maximum.

In subjects that require a hands-on approach, such as biology, these technologies make the learning process more effective and interesting. For example, using digital resources helps students understand abstract topics such as cells, genetic processes, or ecosystems in a visual and interactive way. This approach also increases students' interest, resulting in their active participation in the lesson.

Digital technologies used in biology lessons

1. Mobile applications and software

There are various mobile apps and software available to explain biology topics. For example:

- Khan Academy: Provides interactive videos and quizzes that explain biology topics.
- Quizlet: It is possible to make flashcards and games to remember biology terms.
- Cell Explorer: Used to explore cell structure and functions in 3D format.

These applications allow students to learn subjects in a more visual and interactive way.

2. Simulations and virtual laboratories

Through simulation, students can perform laboratory experiments virtually. For example:

- Labster: Allows students to experiment with genetic engineering, molecular biology, and ecology.
- PhET Interactive Simulations: Provides interactive simulations for topics such as ecology, photosynthesis, and the cell cycle.

These tools eliminate the lack of resources and develop students' ability to experiment.

3. Tools that enhance individual learning

Digital technologies promote personalized learning. In particular, VR (Virtual Reality) and AR (Augmented Reality) technologies are used in biology classes:

- VR technology: Allows students to learn about the internal structure of living organisms by literally

"walking inside". For example, it is possible to visually see the blood circulation of the heart or the photosynthesis process of plants.

- AR technology: Through various mobile applications, students can interactively explore plant, animal or human organs on the device screen.

4. Game-based learning

Game elements make lessons more fun and motivating. Biology games both increase students' interest and help them gain in-depth knowledge of the subject:

- Classcraft: An educational game platform that rewards students for solving biology tasks.
- Minecraft Education Edition: Provides special modules for studying topics such as ecology and biomes.

5. Development of digital skills of teachers and students

Special trainings and courses are organized to improve the skills of teachers to work with digital technologies. This allows them to use innovative methods more efficiently in the teaching process. For students, digital skills are developed through various projects, "STEM" programs and competitions.

We hope that all employees working in the field of education will help in the development of digital skills and 21st century skills in general. After all, we cannot predict what danger awaits our children tomorrow. The way to overcome the difficulties that arise due to special skills and habits is through technological literacy.

Conclusion: Digital technologies make teaching biology lessons more visual, fun and effective. These technologies not only help students better understand the subjects, but also equip them with digital literacy, analytical thinking, and problem solving, which are essential 21st century skills. The use of digital tools in education should be increased, and more resources and training should be provided for both teachers and students. This approach will encourage the improvement of quality in education and the introduction of new generation learning methods. The application of digital skills in biology education makes the teaching process more interactive, engaging and personalized. When a variety of digital tools and resources are made available to students, they are helped to learn more deeply, participate more, and be active in the learning process. The application of these approaches in teaching biology makes it possible to increase the quality of teaching and achieve greater success in the education of students.

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